

Creativity Management: An Approach For Achieving Efficient Workplace Environment

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Abstract

Workplace environment is defined as the current conditions of the surroundings of a workplace. More than 80% of performance problems are influenced by the workplace environment where efficiency of workplace environment represents the total amount of work done by one employee in a single day. There are different types and traits of employees in Architectural Design firms , where only 5 types are being analyzed in this research paper which encounters; creative, innovative ,Talented , Technical & Analytical Architects that should be considered to achieve an efficient workplace environment. Hence , **The Problem of this paper** the inefficient management creating inefficient management for architects results in the dissatisfaction of employees while boosting the rate of turnovers impacting the productivity negatively. One approach that has been introduced to tackle such problem is creativity management which could embrace the 5 types of employees in Architectural design firms. **Thus, the main purpose of this study** is introducing how creativity management approach can effect the workplace environment and increase its efficiency in Architectural design firms . **To achieve the aim of this paper** , a comprehensive literature review analysis has been done on recently published Research papers from 2000 to 2018. This includes discussing the contribution of authors on the approaches for efficient workplace environment , and introducing creativity management approach in workplace environment in Architectural Design firms. Hence, **Findings of this paper** took the form of impact analysis , where the effect of creativity management approach on achieving efficient workplace has been identified.

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Keywords

Workplace environment, Efficient Workplace, Creativity Management, Architectural Design Firms

1. Introduction

Nowadays , Working in any kind of an organization requires a proper environment to be comfortable and creative in order to be efficient and to be more productive , but this workplace could not be found in every organization. Therefore the focus of this research paper is to identify and resemble the concept of a workplace environment considering the

employees needs and satisfaction in order for them to be happy and can be more productive which will result back on the organization in more productivity , profitability and much more. The concept of a workplace environment is not simple as it sounds , it goes through various stages to get to an efficient point where the concept relies and prospers its benefits on the organization.

1.1. The Concept of a Workplace Environment

The term Workplace environment stand for the current conditions of the surroundings of a workplace whether it is the physical environment surrounding the workplace or it is the psychological approach taken in the organization towards its employees. Both terms defines a workplace environment and plays an important role in such environment. To limit the scope of this research paper , The study will focus on the psychological components of a workplace environment where the mentality of employees is considered and taken care of whether its through interactions , management , communication and much more that will be revealed in this research comprehensive literature review. (Work Environment , 2018)

1.2. Efficient Workplace Environment

An Efficient workplace environment is defined as the amount of tasks accomplished by a single employee within a single day, the more tasks accomplished by a single employee within a single day the more efficient the workplace is.(Jane, 2010). Furthermore , in order to achieve an efficient workplace environment, The workplace has to be identified in the first place. For instance , to know the types & trits of employees in a workplace environment. There are various types of employees present in a workplace environment. But this report only focuses on 5 traits of personalities presented in employees already present in the workplace environment. After Analyzing the Current workplace environment , a tool or an approach is needed to accomplish an efficient workplace environment which is described next that this study has been focusing on which is Creativity management, (Croome,2002)

1.3. Latest Trends of Management in Efficient Workplace Environment

Nowadays, there are various of management styles and leadership style has been revealed in all aspects and types of organizations including architectural design firms. For instance, Talent management has become a commonly used management style in various companies all over the world, where this style truly appreciated godly talented people and use their talent in various different structure of work to perform and to produce better results in all fields. Furthermore, lean management as known a Japanese style of management has developed from being a very harsh and strong decisive style of management into a more human need related management where they take in consideration human aspects related to the way of how to manage humans and be a part of the team instead of being the common big boss who only gives order and barely follow up with his teammates.

Finally, the main topic of this research, Creativity management which is considered as a new style of managing employees in organization to perform their imaginative and creative skills to produce new ideas, and not only ideas but ideas that can be practically function or perform. Creativity management is used in various organizations including architectural design firms in other countries and has become a strong factor in determining quality and value of the firm. Creativity management is a strong asset and requires a lot of attention and investment to perform in its best shape. (Alomar, 2010).

1.4. The Role of Creativity Management Towards Embracing Creativity

Embracing creativity in individuals is a fundamental potential that can be found in any human being but needs a motive to move it from the thinking state to functional state. The human resources management can be responsible for choosing creative employees or transforming regular and regular employees to creative ones. HR Management plays on the strings of creativity management, it can determine whether creative people are treated with the right management style to overcome their thinking barriers and complete the work with the best techniques and tools provided or is there a special way and development is needed to be maintained in order to deal with creative people and determines whether an employee is a creative or a non-creative employee. Not only treating the creative people with the right management is the solution, but also transforming the non-creative ones to more creative employees is

an important role that HR management is facing in order to achieve the purpose of creativity management with lowest cost possible and also builds and enhancing employee's skills rather than just disqualify them and replace them with costly qualified people.

Creativity management is related somehow with cost through the last point discussed. Improve the existing employees and reveal their internal creative skills instead of throwing them away and replace them with brand new employees that will cost the firm in both time and money. (Alomar, 2015).

This research resembles a list of questions that will be answered through the research. Questions that describe the problem, purpose and the daily routines from an employee's point of view dealing with management styles in Egyptians organizations especially related to architectural design firms.

1.5. Creativity Management in Architectural Design Firms

Egypt is well known for its architecture and its history in this field particularly, but nowadays the future does not promise as much as the past. There are several problems in various areas related to architectural fields and the development of the deigning & construction procedure. One of the main problem is **The Lack of Creativity Management here in Egypt** and misleading creative people and not appreciating the talent they have and can be developed to achieve unpredictable results. Egypt as well-known as its historical architecture like the pyramids, Luxor & Aswan and many other. Unfortunately, it is also known as it's ugly buildings that are present in every corner of this country. These buildings represent the lack of various aspect but in this case, it strongly lacks the creativity aspect. All buildings are becoming the same, some buildings even left without finishing the exterior layer. For instance, in any design office here in Egypt, let's take residential buildings for an example. There will be one or two designs as a maximum for an apartment or an entire building, and no other alternatives if a problem suddenly shows up. This lack of alternative directly presents the lack of creativity and it management to the firm's employees with other aspects and factors off course included. But the man lack that has to be fixed is the lack of this essential management style. (Danfulani Babangida, 2015).

- How to achieve an Efficient Workplace Environment Through Creativity Management Approach?
- How is Can Workplace Environment Directly Affect The productivity of an Organization ?
- How is Creativity Management related to Architectural design firms?
- What is the difference between Creativity, Talent and Lean Management?
- What kind of expected results from this approach?

1.6. Problem Statement

Management is a method to manage and organize a whole organization and the employees underlying this organization, and it has various styles and types which all focus on one aspect which is a successful and a smooth way of working environment to enhance productivity and quality at minimum cost and time. **The main problem of this research paper is the lack of efficient workplace environment caused by the lack of an appropriate management style that leads to the dissatisfaction of employees and while boosting up the rate of turnovers which eventually leads to a drop in productivity of an organization.** there are various types of management styles used in most of organizations. According to World Business Culture, that analyzed the Egyptian management style. The most common used leadership style in management here in Egypt is bureaucracy, where an authority is clear and the hierarchy of subordinates is clear. Most often in this style, subordinates are never getting include in the decision making, subordinates are only meant to follow rules, even if it was wrong or traditional. Limiting the risk-taking factor is highly cautioned in this kind of management, and being in the comfort state and following the old or mainstream structure of work is approached in this style. According to Kathleen Elkins who analyzed 50 leadership styles in 50 different countries have classified Egyptian leadership style as Nepotism. Nepotism stands for the act of using the power of an authority to get good quality job from people underneath. Refer to fig 2.1 (Elkins , 2016)

his research paper describes a problem that has been here in Egypt for ages without any change or development. The management problem here in Egypt is larger than expected. Managers following the traditional methods from their previous mentors/teachers without realizing the effect of the general output of the organization and that will affect the overall outcome of the country. Creativity Management is a new kind of management style approach that is being used nowadays in other organizations overseas. It can be another solution to the large picture here in Egypt. The lack of knowledge of dealing with creative and talented employees will indeed affect the overall process output during the process and after the process. It is strongly related to the Quality, cost and time of the organization, and plays on the value of each of them. The problem needs to be reviewed all over again from this scope, focusing on creative people, encouraging them and motivating them to reach their highest potential. (Gilbert Tan, 1998)

1.7. AIM

The main purpose of this study is to identify the current workplace environment and change it to an efficient workplace environment to increase job satisfaction related to employees and increase productivity of an organizations through applying the principles of creativity management to manage creative employees within an organization and achieve an efficient workplace environment.

1.8. Research Methodology

Mixed methodologies and techniques have been used to identify the problem and achieve the aim which leads to the results. Firstly, literature review has been undergone, to demonstrate how different literature sources discussed the topic from different approaches used in other countries and some firms here in Egypt that has gone through creativity managed and have experienced managing creative employees in different fields, secondly one to one interviews were made with different companies' representatives that have already managed to use these strategies to magnify their outcomes and productions in different fields , furthermore their daily interactions with different mindsets of employees and how each of them need a special part from creativity managed to be based upon them. Last, employees have been asked about their daily routines and how they are wished to be managed and what do they actually seek from their managers and organization to embrace their potentials in different fields in architectural design firms and other firms as well.

1.9. Scope of Work

The study is carried on in Egypt and specified for Egyptian Architectural Design firms and the Significance of the lack of creativity management in these firms. The study includes the modern era, as of 2018 and afterwards, despite that creativity management has been already practiced in other firms internationally , data and information are collected due these specifications from international and national sources that carry the same scope of work of this study.

1.10. Hypothesis

Architectural Design firms need Creativity Management to be one of their Management Department, if not the prior. Creativity management as explained previously has a direct effect on the success of the business whether through the employee's motivation to work and create new ideas that will steer the wheel of the business better , or through the cost , quality and time effects as discussed previously. Creativity management have been tested through Certain amount of Businesses and Architectural firms , and it see that the type of organizations that has practiced Creativity Management in Their Field , proves that Creativity and creative people actually affects the outcome of the final product and it is essential to take in consideration that factor to improve future outcomes and profitability.

2. Literature Review

Kevin Bacon an American actor has stated "A good director Creates an environment which gives the actor the encouragement to fly" . A beautiful quote that somehow explains that the director is the manager of an organization and his role is to create a work environment to motivate employees to be more productive. Workplace environment is a term that is used to describe the surrounding conditions of the workplace relation with the employee's operation.

Work environment can be of physical factors including office temperature, noise or tools & equipment's such as personal Computers. Work environment also includes psychological factors such as the operations and interaction of employees with other employees' peers or managers that determines the quality of the work environment.

(Work Environment,2018). Since people spend 50% of their time in an indoor environment, employees are very affected by their Work environment that strongly affects their performance & productivity in an organization. (Olanipekun, 2018, Sundstorm,1994).

Efficiency is doing things right. (Drucker, 2010). Efficiency in workplace is defined by the work tasks completed in a single workday by a single employee. The more tasks completed by a single employee in a single workday creates more efficient workplace. (Jane, 2010). Achieving an efficient workplace environment prospers various benefits, on first hand it boosts the productivity of employees, thus boosting the productivity of an organization. According to Akinyele, about 80% of performance problems reside in the work environment of organizations. (Akinyele, 2010).

An efficient workplace environment is developed in a way that allows creativity and productivity work together in parallel and peacefully co-exist. (Jones, 2018) Creativity is the action of transforming new and imaginative ideas and thoughts into reality, as well as creativity is characterized by the ability to receive the world from a different perspective to dig and discover hidden patterns , to make connection between unrelated phenomena. (Naiman and Naiman, 2018). There has been many argues that employee's creativity makes a vital contribution in an organization productivity, therefore organizations need to create a context where it can manage creative ideas and employees and develop a work environment that prospers creativity. (Management,2018)

2.1. Defining Workplace Environment

Workplace environment has a strong influence on the performance and the productivity of an employee. Take for instance, the interactions occurring in a workplace between colleagues during work can motivate other employees or it can destroy their own productivity and distract them from the main aim and goal every organization and achieving it through the performance of its employees. More than 80% of the performance of the employees and the problems occurring that disturb their performance is depending on the workplace environment and it can decide whether the performance of employees is efficient or not, hence the productivity can increase or decrease. (Akinyele,2010). Work environment can be broken down into three sub-environments that affects the manner and the implications of the nature of the work. First is the technical environment where the tools, equipment, infra-structure and other technical elements are included within this type of environment. The other type environment comprises the human environment that interacts with colleagues, teammates and work groups and interactions. The third type is the organizational environment that determines the leadership and management which includes procedures, practices, values and philosophies (Opperman, 2002) (Olanipekun, 2018). This study is determined to find out the implications and procedures taken in organizational environment in order to achieve an efficient workplace that not only increase the whole productivity of employees but also increase the satisfaction of employees, thus also revolving around increase the productivity and performance of employees depending on the type of environment they are working. Refer to **Figure 1** that reveals the three sub-environment every work environment has.

Figure 1, Work Sub environment (Oppermann , 2002)

Workplace environment of an organization can also be broken down into two main categories which influences the environment where employees show their performance at work. First category is external factors which is generally the physical components that influence the work environment and employee's performance. Anything physical that influence the comfort level of employees is considered to be an external factor under the categories. Physical components can be light, noise, temperature, the furniture design of an office where employees work, the presence of plan and greenery in the office and the spatial organization of the office which presents the level of comfort employees are expected to have during their working days. The office should encourage them to work better and increase their performance through comfort factors such as light level that has an effect on the comfortability of employees during performing their job. Other than the external factors that influence the employee's performance to be more productivity, on the other hand the other factor that influence on the employee's performance is the internal factors of an organizational work environment, internal factor is basically composed of phycological and social components that affects the employees state of the ability of performing the job in the best form. Psychological components actually composed of interactions that happen during the working days, such as communications with other colleagues as well as with managers and supervisors, self-motivation and reward system as well as recognition and creativity. All these factors and more are considered interactions within work environment that affects the performance and mental state of an employee. Refer to **figure 2** to get the full picture of work environment factors and components. Other than interaction, there is also distractions that are negative factors that demotivates the employees on doing their job well and influence by decreasing the rate of their performance on doing a particular job. Distractions are generally composed on overly strict policies that expect overload work to produce great result, rather than considered as too much and getting to low quality products will be the result as well as the daily use components such as internet, cell phone, gossip every day distractions should also be eliminated from the work environment as much as possible to avoid these negative components that decrease the rate of efficiency and productivity and thus creating a boring and inefficient working environment that will result in a drop of productivity. (Haynes,2008)For instance, according to Entrepreneur site article about employees satisfaction relation with work environment, about 86% of employees valuing interested work than pay and other 76% of employees rated that the sense of Accomplishment is more important than the par, so satisfaction of employees and their motivation does not only depend on how much their pay is, there is much more than materialistic factor, the sense of recognition and accomplishment given to employees by their managers or supervisor can be much more important according to the

study stated by entrepreneur site article on 5000 employees from different companies around the world. (Al-masri, 2015)

Figure 2, Work Environment Components, (Haynes, 2008)

2.2. Achieving an Efficient Workplace Environment

Efficiency in workplace is defined by the work tasks completed in a single workday by a single employee. The more tasks completed by a single employee in a single workday creates more efficient workplace. (Jane, 2010). Producing an efficient workplace environment is strongly related to increasing the productivity of an organization, the productivity of organization has five main components that are psychologically influenced due to the employees' interactions and how these five components influence the productivity and performance of employees in a workplace, and the managerial process to avoid such problems to identify these five components in the organization and try to fix or replace the symptoms that appear to resolve such a problem. For instance, well-being is the prime main factor that directly affects the productivity of an individual, the other two factors that are very vital as well is the ability to perform a task or a specific job and motivation given to an employee to increase his or her performance. Refer to **figure 3**, to see the observations of psychological factors that influence the productivity of an employee while performing a specific job.

Figure 3, Internal Psychological factors influence rates (Croome, 2002)

A study made on 5000 employees in MENA region including Egypt on the job satisfaction and the performance of employees depending on work environment showed that only 4 out of 10 people are satisfied with. Their work environment and 6 of them are complaining about the influences of their work environment affecting their way of work and decreasing their productivity , as well as more than one fourth of employees are not happy and motivated with their work environment and say that their environment plays a strong role on their demotivation to do their work perfectly . Furthermore , 61% of employees are continuously trying to move to another firm which is creating a continuous cycle of not committing a creating lack of employee’s loyalty to their organization due to the poor work environment of the organization that affect the employees in such a manner that they want to leave their job every now and then. Lastly only 27% of employees believe that their organization care about their well-being which demotivates employees to work perfectly and increase the rate of their performance , if they know they can be replaced within an eye glance. For more illustration , refer to Figure 4.

Figure 4. percentages pie charts (Al-masri , 2015)

In order to create an efficient work environment , knowing the current type of employees at an organization is a vital step to know how to change the work environment to an efficient work environment. Employees are of various types with different personalities and skills. But this study paper has focused on five main types of employees that are at every organization and how much they are influenced and influence a workplace according to their skills level and personality traits.

Creative employees, are those employees that are imaginative and have the ability to generate new ideas and visualized new possibilities and solutions for problems. These employees are the most effected by a work environment , and work environment influence their performance the highest.

Innovative employees, are these employees that take the lead after creative procedures is done by creative employees , innovative employees are employees that implement the new ideas and transform these ideas into reality with new way of thinking and technologies that create a product with minimum effort and cost.

Talented employees, those employees are gifted with a special skills in a special field , these employees cannot multi task they are focused on one task with a particular high skill to perform well , they are not so much influenced by the work environment such as the creative and innovative employees.

Technical employees, those employees are technology seekers , they love technology and software , these employees have the ability to work under high pressure and over loaded tasks to perform a job , these employees are not very affected by their surrounding work environment.

Analytical employees, those employees are analysts thinkers , they have the ability to transform their knowledge and data to graphs and plots , chart and diagrams to know the optimum solution and resolve complicated problems , their work environment is not so much of an importance to them.

Refer to **figure 5** to know the difference between the five types of employees at every organization and **figure 6**, to know how much of an importance work environment to each employee.

Figure 5, Types of employees in an organization. (Haynes, 2008)

Figure 6. percentage of workplace influence on each type. (Haynes, 2008)

2.3. Defininf Creativity, Innovation and Talent

There has always been a confusion between Creativity, Innovation and talent. Either, the three terms are all added up to sum a one term whether it is creativity , innovation or talent. Or, the three terms are confused up and no clue of which one is more efficient , or which term relies on the other. One of the factors that this study shows is a clear definition and separation between the most commonly mistaken and confused terms , and give a clear image about the real sense of each term , and which term relies and depend on the other.

Talent is a well-known term used in everyday routines and work places as well as in educational institutes where students can be differentiated according to their level of talent in a specific subject, or in specific task in work place, or even talent can be doing something entertaining at home. Old English talented, talent an (as a unit of weight), from Latin talent, plural of talented ‘weight, sum of money’, from Greek Talan ton. talent (sense 1) is a figurative use with biblical allusion to the parable of the talents (Oxford Dictionaries | English, 2018). Talent has many colors and skins with different features given to all human beings. **Talent is someone who has a natural ability to be good at something, especially without being taught.** (Dictionary, 2018)

Talents are gifts from god in the form of a person’s calling or natural ability. (Institute for Faith, Work & Economics, 2018). There are factors that directly affect any talent, factors can underlie the support of both emotional and social , the physical environment as well as the targeted remediation. Furthermore, the differentiated instruction and challenging curriculum influence the nature of talent and affect its growth as well. The components of the model shown in **figure 7**, are interacting with one another and act differently according to an individual needs and abilities. (Baum , 2009)

Figure 7, Talent Centered elements (Baum,2009)

Innovation as defined by Cambridge university is the use of a new idea or method as well as the development of new products and designs and lies under any of financial/organizational/technological innovation factors. (Dictionary, 2018). Innovation is actually more of a process that discovers different tools and techniques to uncover modern and new ways to do and create things. In order for innovation to be produced or even exist, it needs Creativity which acts as the seed of innovation. Creativity is the foundation of innovation, and innovation is the process of creativity. (Tools Hero, 2018). From the world perspective, innovation is the improvement of existing or the creation of completely new products , processes or services, as well as the transformation of existing conditions into preferred ones to create a new value for the world. (Spinoglio, 2015). Here are some keys to embrace innovation in an individual or a team. To develop and embrace innovation it has to be directed towards the vision that is desired in the future depending on analytics and data and how to implement these analytics to develop and achieve the desired vision. Refer to **figure 8** (arealityofmyown, 2012).

Figure 8, Components of Innovation (arealityofmyown,2012)

Creativity , the magic word that appears in many business and television advertisements to solve any problem or fix any situation. Well, creativity is not that simple , actually creativity is a science that is based on facts and applications in order to realize what creativity actually means. Creativity is basically the action of transforming new and imaginative ideas and thoughts into reality, as well as creativity is characterized by the ability to receive the world from a different perspective to dig and discover hidden patterns, to make connection between unrelated phenomena. (Naiman and Naiman, 2018). Furthermore, as stated in the dictionary , creativity is the state or quality of being creative , the ability to transcend traditional ideas , rules to meaningful new ideas and forms that underlies creative abilities. (www.dictionary.com, 2018, Oxford Dictionaries | English, 2018). From the famous book human motivation creativity is defined as the tendency to generate or recognize ideas, alternatives or possibilities that may be useful in solving complex problems while entertaining self and others. (Csun.edu, 2018, From Human Motivation, 3rd ed., by Robert E. Franken pg. 396)

Last but not least, the modern definition of creativity Focusing on the individual person, as an aspect of thinking, as a personality constellation, and as an interaction between thinking, personal properties and motivation. This interaction involves a number of paradoxes, in that apparently contradictory elements have to coexist for creativity to emerge (Cromptley, 2015). According to Harvard business school professor, Teresa Aambile , There are three components that define and explore creativity. Creative people in nature spend long period of time learning and developing their skill at a specific field and thus they acquire expertise, they also process and develop creativity thinking skills. However, this is not enough for creativity , the most important component of the three is motivation which can come from outside (extrinsic motivation , via corporate incentives , complements , appreciating the hard work , etc.) and can also come from an inside source (intrinsic motivation , such as passion, purpose or simply fun). (Aambile,2012). Refer to **Figure 9**.

Figure 9, The Three Components of Creativity. (Aambile,2012)

According to the Previous debatable papers and studies. There was a clear evidence that there is a strong relationship between the three terms each in a different aspect or area and field of application. Although, these three terms have been confused lately but recently there were enough evidence based on facts and scientific proves that these terms and debatably meaningful each by its own identity and definition. For instance, if creativity is combined with innovation , a process is formed , a process of transforming the creative generated ideas into reality using new methods and techniques to have a new product. (Finelabs, 2018). Furthermore, if creativity is combined with talent , a creative talent is formed , because talent only is not enough , creativity is needed when new modern and undiscovered ideas are needed . (Jensen, T. 2014). . As well as if talent is combined with innovation , entrepreneur is formed (Klein, E. 2017).. Last but not least, if all terms are combined together , this will result in an enormous growth in productivity whether in business field or in education field or any other field. (Creative Edge. 2013). Refer to **Figure 10**, where an illustration is made to make it clear about the combination between the three terms. As further more refer to figure 2.8 , where a comparison chart is made according to the papers and sources discussing about the three terms in terms of their efficiency , resources process and other in percentages to give a clear sense about the reality of the three terms , as well as refer to table 2.25 , where critical analysis based on the sources collected on each topic discussed to have a clear image about the whole topic and a simplified definitions in terms of the three subjects discussed earlier.

Figure 10, Venn Diagram of the three terms (Klein, E. 2017, Jensen, T. 2014 , Finelabs. 2018)

The following Chart explains the difference between the three terms , creativity , innovation and talents according to number of papers relation to the years these papers has been published to give a clear image about the development of these ideas and opinion through time. **Refer to figure 10.**

Figure 10 , percentage of papers relation of their year of publicity (estimated number according to the sources & papers gathered)

As shown in the last figure 10, a high percentage of number of papers has discussed creativity importance and relevance during period from 2012-2018 , as well as Talent with a 28.5% of total papers during 2009-2018 and Innovation with the same rate but during 2012-2018. As a result, Creativity shows a high importance due to the number of papers debating over the components and programs of how to imply and develop creativity in everyday routine. Another comparison shown in **figure 11**, shows the rate of effectiveness of each type and the skills needed in order to produce a noticeable effect on the project or output. The relation shown is based on the paper and resources collected to generate an organized and final results comparing between the three types in different fields.

Figure 11, The relation between effectiveness with skills needed in each type (Baum,2009) (Spinogolio,2012) (Naiman,2018)

As shown in the last **figure 12**, there is high effectiveness of creativity compared with talent and innovation , not only that but also requires minimum skills and have high effect upon an output. While talent requires high skills in order to perform that kind of talent and to have a noticeable effect on an output, inspire with innovation also requires a relevant skills amount but have high effect on an output than a talent does. Furthermore, another figure 3.1 shows a relation between the resources needed in order to generate ideas. This relation has proved that there is a quite difference when inspecting each term on different level of resources limitation but there are fixed values in order the effect of each type on generating ideas in percentages.

Figure 12, The relation between resources needed and the ideas generation output of each type (Baum,2009) (Spinogolio,2012) (Naiman,2018)

As shown in the previous figure, that creativity requires minimum resources in order to perform and generate new ideas that have a noticeable effect on the progress of the process. While talent and innovation need a considerable amount of resources to start them and get an effect level according generating and stimulating ideas on an output or final product. Last but not a least, a **figure 13** that shows the effect of work environment on each type according to their performance. For instance , creativity could be very sensitive to its work environment , as colleagues and teammates affect creative people on a mark able level and can cause confusion in the idea generation phases.

The Effect of work environment of the performance of each type

Figure 13, The effect of work environment of the performance of each type of each type (arealityofmyown,2012) (Csun,2018) (Aambile,2012) (Baum,2009)

As shown in the last figure , creativity has scored 60% according to the impact and effect of work environment on creativity that proves creativity is the most of three types that is most likely to be very sensitive to its work surrounding and environment. While talent and innovation has much lower impact of work environment , regardless of what innovation has scored that proves it also has a higher impact from work environment comparing it with talent which has the least impact from work environment.

The next **Table 1**, shows the different resources and papers that has discussed the three terms innovation , talent and creativity. According to their components, definitions and elements as well as these papers has been classified and organized in order to get a clear image about the differences of the three terms. The next table is categorized according to the paper topic and publisher as well as the year it has been published in. Furthermore , critical analysis has been provided to analyze and criticize the content each paper is carrying in order to clarify the image more often.

Table 1. Shows the resources and papers discussed in the previous topics

Papers/Authors	Year	Topic	Critical Analysis
	Talent		
Oxford Dictionary	2018	Definition of Talent	Natural ability to be good at something , especially if not taught.
Cambridge Dictionary	2018		
Institute for Faith , Work & Economics	2018	The precise definition of talent	Talents are gifts from god in the form of a person’s calling or natural ability.

Table 1 continued

Innovation			
Cambridge Dictionary	2018	Innovation Meaning	A new idea or method
Tools Hero	2018	What is innovation?	Innovation is actually more of a process that discovers different tools and techniques to uncover modern and new ways to do and create things
Spinoglio	2015	Definition of innovation	innovation is the improvement of existing or the creation of completely new products
Creativity			
Naiman	2018	What is Creativity?	Creativity is basically the action of transforming new into reality, by the ability to receive the world from a different perspective discover hidden patterns.
Dictionary Oxford Dictionaries	2018	The Definition of Creativity	creativity is the quality of being creative , the ability to transcend traditional ideas , meaningful new forms that underlies creative abilities.
Csun	2018	What is Creativity?	tendency to generate ideas , alternatives or possibilities that may be useful in solving complex problems while entertaining self and others.
Cropley	2015	Definition of creativity	Focusing on the individual person, as an aspect of thinking, , personal properties and motivation.
Combination of three terms			
Klein E	2017	Talent-Innovation Development	When talent is combined with innovation , entrepreneur is formed
Jensen Finelabs	2014 2018	Collaborative Creativity Innovation research and Training	Creativity combined with talent , gives creative talent and when combined with innovation gives a process
Creative Edge	2013	Creative Steps	When all the three terms are combines it peaks up the productivity of any organization.

According to the previous papers and resources and the previous table 1 that has clarified the differences between the three terms , the next table 2 is a separating component in order to differentiate the advantages and disadvantages of each term. The next table concludes and justify why creativity in specific has been chosen to be the most reliable option of all three terms , in terms of efficiency , productivity and overall benefits.

Table 2. Pros & cons of each Term (Robinson,2018)

	Talent	Innovation	Creativity
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Competence to finish a subject + Develop new ways to synthesize information + Thrive when only motivated + promote productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> +Productivity +Competitiveness +Personal value and status +New relationships +profitability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Problem solving + Connect with other people + Expanded sense of time , +Self-awareness & Expression + Freedom +Stress relief +Multidisciplinary , it benefits almost all professions + Give sense of Purpose + Confidence and risk taking + Fun
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Needs a considerable amount of motivation to extract the talent -needs much time and effort to finish a task -very emotional -Act as victims -seeking perfectionism -talents depend on availability -not multitask Not talented in different fields -needs much resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -very expensive to apply -too much investments -might waste resources -might ruin reputation if product is poor - needs time and effort -needs much resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Too many ideas to apply may take a lot of time -Too many ideas may cause confusion and decrease focus -Saturation of ideas -Might affect quality if not done efficiently

As shown in the table 2, Creativity is the most efficient component of all three, due to it has various advantages and comes with least downsides that are although fixable. Creativity has shown that it is very efficient and it can draw up a new margin of success and achievements if it is implemented in the right conditions with the right tools and techniques. As shown creativity is best at problem solving and generating new ideas on a continuous manner but as well too much ideas can cause a creative person much confusion, so ideas has to be limited to an exceeding limit and not further because too much ideas will also cause saturation , the ideas will not be valid anymore due to much confusion and lack of focus. Generating new ideas is great but limiting them into sufficient amount increases the chance of these ideas actually working and practiced in real life applications. (Higonia, 2016) (Robinson, 2018)

2.4. Latest Trends of Managerial Procedure for an Efficient Workplace.

Recent Organizations and firms are aiming for higher productivity and profitability , and the focus of the firms is circulating around the main head of management , to achieve better efficient management process , the HR management role has become more of an important status to control and maintain the management process and the

teams that are being selected to perform efficiently under the management processes in order to gather as much as possible of value knowledge and new techniques to keep up with the ongoing updated market , as well as to ensure that the firm is significant enough to perform and compete among other firms and competitors. Latest trend of management process has been development through the years of expertise and development. Which underlies of these three-management process, despite that there are various other efferent management processes , but this research papers are focused on three management process to maximize the focus on the scope and to keep up with goal orientation of this study. Management processes are of which lean management that is originally a Japanese management process developed by Toyota , Talent management that development and focused on talent and innovation of employees , and lastly and most recently creativity management which is the focus of this research paper and the following debatable discussions , determines why the study focuses and preferred creativity management to be one of the most efferent management processes among other management styles.

Lean Management is widely known in the business world, and has influenced many businesses in various ways. The origin of lean management comes from the management philosophy developed from Toyota production system (TPS). Lean management is simply defined as the process of focusing on improving the speed and quality through reduction of process wastes. Lean management most common used teams will be problem solving and Self-directed teams. (Schultz, 2015). Lean management is a method of managing companies that adapt to the actual market status through organizational and functional alternations. The core of lean management is the act of polishing up the company, especially in the company’s assets and its management styles. Furthermore, lean management focuses on training and shaping the employee’s attitudes keeping in consideration positive public relations this method pays important focus to the factors concerning HR management. (Dekier, 2012). Understanding the philosophy requires to understand lean management process , because lean management is a cultural continuous improved practiced at every level by all teams of the organizations as well as lean is the respect of the customer voice , furthermore , it is the elimination of waste in all its forms and focusing on only improving the work process .Key elements of lean management are simple to apply and can be applied on any firms , all it needs a professional manager that can control the atmosphere of the management process. Refer to **figure 14**, Lean Management Key Elements

- Apply strong leadership governance
- Engage staff fully in daily improvement
- Coach the staff and transfer lean skills
- Measure the right things and make results visible
- Embed standard work into the culture. (Zaidi,2016)

Figure 14. Lean Management Key Elements (Soar,2018)

Talent Management the process of finding, developing, training, and keeping employees whose skills best align with the needs and objectives of the company. The goal of talent management is to hire the best employees the business can afford so that the company reaches its maximum potential for success. It is made of phases that are characterized and emphasized towards the employees needs and the success of the business.

Workforce planning, recruiting process, onboarding, performance management, Training and performance support, Succession planning, compensation and benefits, Critical skills gap analysis.

Layla Atae, 2013. Approach to talent management is designed to meet wider strategic needs. Focuses on getting maximum benefit consistent . only 33 % of organizations , business leaders and HR work together to set a talent strategy that is closely aligned with and enables business strategy. Three pout of five say their organizations should reappraise their talent management approaches to stay consistent with business needs , every six months or an ongoing basis. Talent management is often assigned based on availability rather than specific skills and experience. (PMI , 2014). The process of talent management requires certain steps in order to perform talent management right and to avoid any future confusion or mistakes. The steps of the process are as the follows.

- Retain (Role matching , Special projects & Roles)
- Recruit (Role profiles , talent insights)
- Select (Gap report , comparison reports)
- Deploy (Role profiles , Job/Talent , Comparison)
- Develop (Personal Skills , Competencies) .

Consequences that might arrive with the process of talent management is that available talent will miss business expectations , stand alone or homemade assessments, instinctual decisions are left to chance , hr. fail to meet business talent needs , Voluntary Turnovers will occur according to the top performers. Refer to figure 15 , that illustrates the process of talent management in a clearer scope. (Soar, 2018)

Figure 15, Talent Management Key Elements (Soar,2018)

Creativity management is defined as management processes that aims at increasing goals , evaluation and new ideas preparations for further implementation in organizations. While many organizations already affect the creativity of their employees and managers (and not always in a supportive way), the point of creativity management is to make

processes that do so explicit and increase creativity and innovation. As mentioned earlier, an important and current focus is to induce lower officials to act with increased creativity and initiative. (Berman, 2005)

Creativity management process acquires several phases that has to be undergone to guarantee a healthy and well-functioning of creativity management. Creativity management can be the foundation for innovation processes in the future, but in order to innovate in a correct manner , the foundation should be built in a form where it can hold strengths for further implementations Refer to **figure 16** Creativity management process in summery is a fundamental six phases that requires focus and order of each phase. And they are as the following:

- Idea Generation & Evaluation
- Orientation & Training
- Incentives & Rewards
- Appraisal & Evaluation Processes
- Individual Appraisal Process
- Department Evaluation Process (Berman,2005)

Figure 16, Creativity Management Process. (Berman,2005)

Creativity management is considered to be more of a complex process than it sounds, but comes with its great results and benefits over the firm/organization or business. To understand creativity management and understand how to manage creative people, the foundation of understanding creativity itself must be built first. Creativity has always been known with the phrase “thinking out of the box” but in fact creativity is a broad approach than this , it is an approach supported by ideas and experiences. Furthermore, adapting new fresh thinking. Creative people usually ignore the criticism despite them following the criticism to its conclusion, But the comments of their colleges at work can affect them not in a negative way by driving their ideas into a different conclusion. Therefore, the environment

surrounding and supporting creative teams can have an enormous impact on creative people. Creativity can be best understood if it is divided into two terms. (Patmore,2009). Refer to figure 2.3.3.1.

- Visual thinking (The mind’s ability to have a different sight of a totally new situation)
- Problem Solving (when solving a problem, a problem is divided into smaller problems , hence ‘sub-problems’ where it can be more easier and flexible to understand and requires much less effort to fix)

Furthermore, there are some guidelines to encourage and enable creativity within the team by examining leadership, structure and culture in more details as following.

- Leadership style – must be participative leadership, democratic and non- authoritarian style.
- The job - should provide the employee with both attention and freedom
- Organizational structure - a non-hierarchical, flat structure with no perceivable boundaries
- Culture - supportive and risk-taking culture , open to new ideas and encouraging nontraditional
- Thinking
- Attitude - adjustable, thoughts sharing and able to work around pre developed
- Ideas
- Skills - skilled in terms of knowledge, learning, and creativity techniques
- Value - understanding and valuing employee creativity. (Patmore,2009)

Guidelines to Enable Creativity in an Organization

Figure 17, Guidelines to enable Creativity in an Organization (Berman,2005)

Table 3. Shows the resources and papers discussed in the previous topics

Papers/Authors	Year	Topic	Critical Analysis
Master Thesis in Business Administration (Shcultz,M)	2015	Lean’s Impact On Innovation	Lean management is simply defined as the process of focusing on improving the speed and quality through reduction of process wastes. Lean management most common used teams will be problem solving and Self-directed teams.

Table 2 continued

ResearchGate, (Dekier.L)	2012	The origin & Evolution of Lean Management System	earn management focuses on training and shaping the employee's attitudes keeping in consideration positive public relations this method pays important focus to the factors concerning HR management.
Lean Management, (Zaidi.A)	2016	Lean Management Process	Apply strong leadership governance Engage staff fully in daily improvement Coach the staff and transfer lean skills Measure the right things and make results visible Embed standard work into the culture.
Ataee.L	2013	Talent Management	Workforce planning, recruiting process, onboarding, performance management, Training and performance support, Succession planning, compensation and benefits, Critical skills gap analysis.
PMI	2014	Talent Management	Talent management is often assigned based on availability rather than specific skills and experience.
Soar Community	2018	Talent management	Consequences that might arrive with the process of talent management is that available talent will miss business expectations , stand alone or homemade assessments, instinctual decisions are left to chance , hr. fail to meet business talent needs , Voluntary Turnovers will occur according to the top performers. Refer to figure 2.31 , that illustrates the process of talent management in a clearer scope.
Researchgate, (Berman.E.M)	2005	Creativity Management in Public Organizations	the point of creativity management is to make processes that do so explicit and increase creativity and innovation. As mentioned earlier, an important and current focus is to induce lower officials to act with increased creativity and initiative.

Based on the previous data and sources through papers gathered information, it has been clear enough. That Talent, lean and creativity management are a very different approaches and each require a different type and style of leadership, therefore each of them require a unique organizational structure where , the delegation and team work takes place in order for an organization to be functional. Each Type of management has its own organizational structure. For instance, Talent Management uses Matrix Organizational structure for that the work is Transferred through several manager and each manager is responsible for a certain number of employees working in a field where they can embrace their talents. As for Lean management, this type of management is very direct and it throws all its concentration and focus on the customer satisfaction and the value of the product an organization produce. A flat Organizational structure is an optimum solution for a lean management organization, where work is directed for each one specialized in his/her field without any delegation or excessive amount of work depended on small number of people. Lastly is the chosen management that has been analyzed thoroughly in this study , Creativity management where team work is vital , Leadership styles are participative and non-authorized leadership style , ideas must flow through the whole organization in order to achieve a function creativity management organization and in order to achieve and enable creativity within an organization , for this to happen , the non-hierarchal organizational structure is the most optimum solution and structure for creativity management to allow ideas flow freeline to the whole organization and to create an environment of team-work and motivation. This structure gives a sense of freedom to

the employees , where they can embrace their ideas as well as to share their ideas with each other and with the whole organization. Refer to **Table 3.** (Al-senosity ,2014) (Organizational Structure, 2009).

Table 4.Organizational Structures of each management Style. (Al-senosity ,2014) (Organizational Structure, 2009).

<p>Talent Management</p>
<p>Matrix Organizational Structure</p>
<p>Lean Management</p>
<p>Flat Organizational Structure</p>
<p>Creativity Management</p>
<p>Non-Hierarical Organizational Structure</p>

2.5. Creativity management application in Architectural Firms

Architecture is the art and science of aligning cities and building to actually fit the lives we want to live, the process of encouraging our society into the physical world. (Ingels , 2014). According to MSI database a research was done on industries on the level of creativity it requires, and architecture has been placed in the 2nd position industry with 33% that requires creativity in its organization, Refer to figure X. As Architecture field is not like any other business field, it requires a different style of management and specified directions for its employees, as usually the employees in architectural firms are more creative and innovative than other fields , because it requires them to come up with new ideas for projects and problem solving as well as the novelty and originality of the ideas is a very important issue in the design field. Moreover, not only the novelty of ideas is important but also its functionality and its adaptive levels to reality scenes. An architect is required to satisfy the needs of the client through his creative thinking and designs, therefore a management is required to manage architects and increase the efficiency of the workplace environment they are working in , so they are more productive and hence the productivity of the firm will boost when the architect or employee is well satisfied and motivated to accomplish goals and achieve tasks. Refer to **figure 18**.

Figure 18. The Creative Engine Bar Chart (EMSI,2012)

In working with creative architects , a management must be considered to recognize and appreciate creativity. Creativity management is the central role of management to release creativity and develop its core impact on quality, productivity and turn on profits. Furthermore, creativity management is an effective management that fits any architectural firm as it is well consistent with the goals of both employees/architects and the firm itself.

Those who have successfully managed to enhance and increase creativity suggest the following guidelines to get the optimum creativity level from architects as well as other employees. (Torrance, 1964)

- Motivation towards goals
- Maximize the flow of communication
- Recognition of subordinates
- Give creative architects some time alone
- Help creative architects to feel secure and confident
- Tolerate Failure
- Special direction for employees
- Respect out of the box thinking

- Motivate free flow of ideas
- Provide creative work environment
- Reward system for creative achievement
- Evaluate creative ideas as soon as possible
- Allow freedom for creative people in their workplace environment.

After looking up for the guidelines go how to manage the architects in an architectural firms , it is also of importance to re-organize the whole organization to be collaborated with creativity and encourage of spreading creativity in the whole organization , according to B.Miller of *Managing innovation for growth and profit (1970)* suggested that a company department should be established to report and evaluate new ideas and information generated from employees within an organization and then this department after evaluating new ideas , it could be passed to the top level management and also a division could also provide training and counseling for managers at every level in all divisions serving as a coordinator of innovation regularly measuring creativity in all other departments and making conclusions and remarks to top management.

Furthermore, there are various techniques to foster and enhance creativity thinking within an organization to encourage new idea generation and implementation. The most common of these techniques is brainstorming where a group approach to a problem and try to find and evaluate solutions with the greatest number of alternatives. There are many other techniques than brainstorming, for instance Cataloging ,checklists , attribute lists , free association , forced relationships , morphological analysis , and lastly input-output techniques .All of these techniques are listed in the following chart with a brief description of each technique. (Miller, 1977)

2.6. Results and Findings

This Study conducted the main feature of a workplace environment and how to achieve an efficient workplace environment through applying the application of creativity management in architectural firms and other organizations. The upcoming charts shows the results of the impact of creativity management and how the management of creative people have changed their work environment efficiency and thus boosted their job satisfaction and their productivity in an organization. According to a study conducted by forrester consulting commissioned by Adobe in 2014. 58% of survey respondents said their firms enhance creativity had 2013 revenues exceeding their 2012 revenues by 10% or more. Another survey also showed that 69% of firms applying the principles of creativity management had national recognition for being the best place to work. Moreover, 82% of companies around the world claims that creativity management gain greater business benefits like revenue growth and market share. Another Study shows satisfied employees increase productivity by 12% and high level of engagement to their workplace increase the operating income by 19% and the earnings growth by 28%. Refer to **figure 19**. (Forrester consulting, 2014).

Figure 19. Enhanced Creative Firms Analysis (Forrester Consulting , 2014)

The Figure 19 shows a chart that presents how influenced Enhanced Creative firms are by creativity management and how much of an impact it has on the workplace environment of a firm. The first bar shows that 58% of firms that uses the application of creativity management has a 10% increase over their revenue compared by their last year revenue, and the middle bar shows that 69% of the enhanced creative firms has a better workplace environment influenced by their application of creativity management. Last bar shows that 82% of these firms has an increase in their revenue growth and market share due to their application of creativity management and an efficient workplace environment. (Forrester Consulting, 2014)

As for **Figure 20**, it represents the impact of satisfied employees over the success of an organization which is due implementing creativity management techniques and applying an efficient workplace environment. The satisfaction of employees is very important it can change values , numbers , profits of an organization. Therefore as shown in the chart if employees are well satisfied the productivity of a firm is boosted by 12% which is a reasonable increase in the rate and level of productivity within the whole organization. Moreover , a 19 percent increase in operating income of an organization which makes sense as long as there is high job satisfaction and job engagement of employees within the organization. Furthermopre , a 28 percent increase in the earning growth of an organization , job satisfaction is indeed helpful for the growth of an organization especially it was a startup organization. Last but not least studies have proven that it is 37 percent boosting rate in the sales level of an organization according to the levelof satisfaction of its employees. (Business & Personal Growth, 2014)

Figure 20, Satisfied Employees Benefits Analysis (Business & Personal Growth, 2018)

3. Methodology

This section of the study research explains and describes the methodologies used and practiced while depriving the data and information to be based on facts and proofs, to identify the problem and that it has a real effect on the scope of the research. A problem restatement is also provided to assure the existence of the problem, proving it with facts deprived from methodology practiced that has been done in this research study. A background of methodologies techniques has been explained, to give a justified reason of choosing the methodology technique in order to collect

data and base information to identify the problems and its roots in the current scope of the research paper. Furthermore , a detailed methodology approach is also explained , on how the data and information collection procedures has been practiced and under what condition and circumstances and the rate of practices it was done on , for instance if it was interview , when and where and who was interview and how much employees and people interviewed in order to base the research problem on their point of view and collect data and information from their own perspectives and aspects of their own problems relations with the research problem and identity.

3.1. Background on Research Methodologies

In research, two primary methodologies exist to do it, either subjective or quantitative approach. Quantitative Research has the fundamental goal of information measurement. It gives estimation of occurrence of different sentiments or perspectives because of results' speculation on a test of intrigue. Now and again, this dimension of research is trailed by subjective research for further investigation of discoveries. Subjective research centers around picking up top to bottom comprehension of main drivers of issues or basic inspirations or reasons. It unwinds an issue's motivation or on the other hand setting. Besides, much of the time it creates speculations and thoughts for later quantitative investigation or research. (Atlasti, 2017) Joining both subjective and quantitative investigation together can be a third methodology embraced. For instance, this can be accomplished if the examination of research is fundamentally quantitative; notwithstanding, a 'human touch' is included utilizing interviews. This can be gainful as to explicit patterns or indicating what explicit factors or issues intend to individuals along the quantitative examination and discoveries. Subjective discoveries can give great thinking of quantitative discoveries also now and again. Another model in which quantitative and subjective can be coordinated is in evaluative contextual analyses. The information gathered for this assessment incorporate quantitative information and diverse information accumulation techniques can be utilized to give examined, extensive discoveries from alternate points of view.

3.2. 3.2 Lack of Efficient Workplace Environment.

The problem discussed earlier in this research, is the lack of an efficient work environment in Egyptian firms which decrease the productivity and employee's satisfaction which leads to declination in the effectiveness and productivity of an organization. and how to fill/fix this lack with techniques and managerial style to give a better work environment for better job satisfaction and productivity of the whole organization. Furthermore, 80% of the performance problems occurring in everyday work is the work environment and its influence on the employee's performance.(Akinyele,2010)As stated before that a study made on 5000 employees in MENA region including Egypt on the job satisfaction and the performance of employees depending on work environment showed that only 4 out of 10 people are satisfied with. Their work environment and 6 of them are complaining about the influences of their work environment affecting their way of work and decreasing their productivity, as well as more than one fourth of employees are not happy and motivated with their work environment and say that their environment plays a strong role on their demotivation to do their work perfectly . Furthermore, 61% of employees are continuously trying to move to another firm which is creating a continuous cycle of not committing a creating lack of employee's loyalty to their organization due to the poor work environment of the organization that affect the employees in such a manner that they want to leave their job every now and then. Lastly only 27% of employees believe that their organization care about their well-being which demotivates employees to work perfectly and increase the rate of their performance, if they know they can be replaced within an eye glance. (AL-masri , 2015)

3.3. 3.3. Research Methodological Approach.

The Methodology approach of this paper was a mix of qualitative and quantitative approaches. Where in quantitative approach focused on data collection from sources and other scientific papers that identifies the main scope of the problem and practices done to recover form the problem and avoid it in the future in the identical scope of the research paper where the main problem is the lack of efficient workplace environment in Egyptian firms , furthermore statistical analysis was also provided and collected from scientific papers.

The qualitative approach was based on the people point of view on the scope of the problem and the level of their understanding to the issue , and observations on the experiences they have dealt with their working lives in different

firms facing the same problem. This qualitative approach was done with interviews and questionnaires on how the problem is affecting their way of work and how did the problem affect them.

Qualitative research approach was utilized on the grounds that such an apparatus comprehends fundamental motivations to an issue or circumstance which works as one in surveying the impact of recuperating inside plan on work environment fulfillment. The effect on employee's performance depends the work environment they are working in , and along these lines such relations furthermore, observations require top to bottom comprehension and examination further past than measurement that a quantitative technique can give. Regardless of that, quantitative examination or research technique was gone for in measuring the regular responses to specific inquiries giving a sign of the degree of legitimacy of variables or answers to employees and a sign with respect to what implies most to employees. To sum things up, quantitative gave insights with respect to which factors exist increasingly and which mean most to clients while subjective gave the reason and comprehension of how and why such factors influenced employee's performance and productivity. The subjective investigation helped in creating needs. The two primary information accumulation techniques received were organized meetings and top to bottom subjective meetings. Organized meetings were utilized as a quantitative instrument in meetings and reviews with staff (engineers, architects, employees, managers), while the subjective in-depth interviews were embraced in the meeting with employees and getting from them the real picture on the main problem and the variable solutions that can be conducted to solve such problem ana aim at achieving an efficient workplace environment to increase the employees' level of satisfaction. And the overall productivity of the organization.

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